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“APPRAISAL OF ANTIBIOTICS USE IN A SECONDARY CARE HOSPITAL IN SOUTH INDIA.

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ABSTRACT

The emergence of antibiotic resistant bacteria is major problem throughout the world and rational use of antibiotics is therefore very important. Good infection control practice is a critical component for success of such programme. This six months prospective observational study was designed to evaluate the appropriateness of antibiotic use in a secondary care referral hospital of South India. The data of all in patients (n=100) were collected by obtaining a proper consent. Maximum of 52.78% patients had culture sensitivity test being done, which may taken as a indication for being rational. The results revealed that the purpose of antibiotics prescribed was for prophylaxis (15%), empirically (37%) and therapeutically 48%. In the study population (n=49) (patients had shown a positive culture study reports for urine, sputum, pus and blood samples), totally 110 antibiotics were prescribed, 71.88% on dual therapy and 28.12% were on three antibiotics and the mean number of antibiotics prescribed was 2.28. In the overall population, 61.65% were administered intravenously and 39.35% of oral antibiotics The major organisms identified were E.coli (28.90%) and amikacin had shown the highest sensitivity in E.coli (86.4%). Totally 31 drugs of antibacterials were listed in National List of Essential Medicine. Out of 31, 15 antibacterials were prescribed in study population.

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INTRODUCTION

Antibacterial medications are considered as the greatest discovery of the twentieth century. The word "antibiotics" comes from the Greek word anti ("against") and bios ("life"). The first antimicrobial was discovered in the mid-20 and many new molecules were discovered between 1960 and 1980. This 'golden era of antibiotics' saw a dramatic fall in the mortality from infections. Since the 80's, not many new class of molecules have been discovered and the funding into antimicrobial research is on the decline and now deaths due to resistant infections is slowly increasing; mortality due to nosocomial infections is now 4 times that due to road traffic accidents¹.

Rational drug use (RDU) is conventionally defined as the use of an appropriate, efficacious, safe and cost-effective drug given for the right indication in right dose and formulation, at right intervals and for the right duration of time.

Rational Use of Antibiotics

WHO defines rational use of drug as "Rational use of drugs requires that patients receive medications appropriate to their clinical needs, in doses that meet their own individual requirements for an adequate period of time, and the lowest cost to them and their community."².

Empirical therapy:

Empirical antibacterial therapy should be restricted to critical cases, when time is inadequate for identification and isolation of the bacteria and reasonably strong doubt of bacterial infection exists: septicemic shock/ sepsis syndrome, immune compromised patients with severe systemic infection, hectic temperature, neutrophilic, leukocytosis, raised ESR etc. In such situations, drugs that cover the most probable infective agent/s should be used.

Prophylactic therapy:

Antimicrobial prophylaxis is administered to susceptible patients to prevent specific infections that can cause definite detrimental effect. These include anti-tubercular prophylaxis, anti rheumatic prophylaxis, anti endocarditis prophylaxis and prophylactic use of antibacterial in invasive medical procedures etc. In all these situations, only narrow spectrum and specific drugs are used. It should be remembered that there is no single prophylaxis to 'prevent all' possible bacterial infections.⁴

Organism causing Infections

S. No.	Organisms	Causes
Gram Positive		
1	Staphylococcus Epidermis	Septicaemia and Endocarditis
2	Staphylococcus Aureus	Bloodstream Infections, Pneumonia, or Bone and Joint Infections
3	Staphylococcus Albus	Wound Infection and in Septicaemia
4	Streptococcus Pneumoniae	Pneumonia, Bacteremia, Otitis Media, Meningitis, Sinusitis, Peritonitis and Arthritis.
5	Streptococcus Pyogenes	Pharyngitis or Impetigo but, In rare cases, can also Cause Invasive Diseases such as Cellulitis, Bacteremia, Necrotizing Fasciitis, and Toxic Shock Syndrome
6	Clostridium Tetani	Tetanus
7.	Clostridium Botulinum	Food borne Botulism, Wound Botulism, Infant botulism, Adult Infectious Botulism, Inadvertent
Gram Negative		
1.	E. coli	UTI, Gastroenteritis, Cholecystitis, Bacteremia, Cholangitis, Pneumonia, Neonatal Meningitis, Infected Bones and Joints, and Skin and Soft Tissue Infections
2.	Pseudomonas	Pneumonia, UTIs, and Bacteremia
3.	Salmonella Typhi	Typhoid
4.	Enterobacteria	Pneumonia, Urinary Tract Infections and Skin Infections
5.	Helicobacter Pylori	Gastritis and Peptic Ulcer

AIM:

The study entitled "Appraisal of Antibiotics Use in A Secondary Care Hospital In South India" was aimed to achieve the following objectives.

OBJECTIVE

- To analyze the prescribing pattern of antibiotics.
- To evaluate the appropriateness of antibiotics used.
- To identify the most prevalence organism and its sensitivity and resistance pattern.

METHODOLOGY

STUDY SITE:

All the wards of General Medicine, Care & Supportive Centre and General Surgery departments of a 300 bedded hospital.

STUDY DESIGN

Prospective Observational Study.

STUDY PERIOD

06 months.

PLAN OF THE STUDY**Phase I:**

Submission of protocol and obtaining consent from hospital authority.

Literature Survey:

The literatures supporting the study were gathered from various sources such as: British Medical Journal, American Medical Journal, Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics, Journal of Pharmacy Practice, The Annals of pharmacotherapy, Journals of antimicrobial chemotherapy, Journal of national medical association, Indian journal on medical microbiology.

Design of: Data Entry form, Patient Information& Consent Form:**Data Entry Form**

A separate data entry form for incorporating inpatient details were designed and the format contains provision to enter the details such as name, age, sex, height, weight, in patients . No, date of admission, date of discharge, vital signs, reason for admission, past medical history, past medication history, and any predisposing factors. Provision was given in the format for entry of details like Blood sugar levels, Blood counts, Liver function test, Renal function test, Electrolytes, Urine examination, Lipid profile, Diagnosis, Drug chart, ADR monitoring chart and Drug interaction chart and dose and any interventions.

Patient Information Form has been prepared, to inform the patients or the care givers about the purpose and the necessity of the study by providing the patient information form and assured them that the confidentiality will be strictly maintained and also it will help the betterment of patients' health.

Patient Consent Form has also been prepared and written consent was collected from all the patients or from the caregivers by using patient consent form after providing the information about the study.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients of either sex who were getting admitted to the study site during study period and were prescribed with at least one antibiotic and in whom the culture sensitivity test is performed.

Exclusion Criteria: The patients who all are unwilling to participate in the study and terminally ill, will be not included in the study.

Phase II: Data collection through standard data entry format.

Literature survey.

Data analysis.

Evaluate the appropriateness of antibiotics use.

Analyze the prescribing pattern of antibiotics.

Application of statistical tools

Phase III:

Literature survey.

Data Analysis

The obtained data will be thoroughly analyzed to evaluate the appropriateness of antibiotic use and utilization pattern of antibiotics and drug interactions will also be noted. Statistical Analysis Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 11.0.) ANOVA tests were used to study differences between group's variables of age, number of drugs prescribed, number of antibiotics prescribed and length of stay. ANOVA test was performed using number of subjects, mean and standard deviation. P value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Association between the age, number of drugs and length of stay were done by Pearson's correlation coefficient.

RESULT & DISCUSSION

The study site had 100 patients as per inclusion and exclusion criteria. 49 patients had shown a positive culture study reports for urine, sputum, pus and blood samples. Distribution of patients in various departments and their status on cultural sensitivity were thoroughly analyzed and reported in table 2.

Table. 2. Distribution of patients in various departments and their status on cultural sensitivity.

S.No.	Departments	Overall (n=100)	Study(n=49)	% culture Sensitivity
1	General medicine	44	22	50%
2	Care & Supportive centre	27	13	48.15%
3	Surgical	29	14	48.28%

The results on Gender categorization had revealed that both the overall and study population had a predominantly male patients. The same was given in the Figure. 1.

Fig.1 Gender Categorization.

The overall population and the study population were categorized based on their age and results were given in Table No.3. From the results it was understood that in both overall and study population patients in Late adulthood (51-65) were found to be more.

Table.3.Age Categorization.

S. No.	Age group (range in yrs)	Overall (n=100)	Study (n=49)
1	Early adulthood (19-35)	08	04
2	Adulthood (36-50)	22	11
3	Late adulthood (51-65)	41	20
4	Young old (66-74)	23	11
5	Old (75-84)	06	03

Smoker were seen to have an increase risk of contracting infections, especially those of the respiratory system, leading to an increased use of antibiotics result of which been tabulated in Table.4.

Table.4.Social history.

S. No.	Social history	Overall n=100	Study n=49
1	Smoker	18	09
2	Alcoholic	15	07
3	Tobacco	06	03
4	None of the above	61	30

In the overall population, the most common condition diagnosed was found to be 44% of all Respiratory Tract Infections and 19% of UTI. The study population had 4.41 % UTI, 3.92% LRTI, 1.96% asthma. The details of other diagnosis were given in the Table No.5. A similar result was obtained by Rashid et al (2011) who had reported that the major indications for antibiotics were diseases of the respiratory system (28%).

Table.5. Diagnosis.

S. No.	Type of diseases	Overall (n=100)	Study (n=49)
1	LRTI	16	08
2	COPD	04	02
3	Asthma	08	04
4	TB	12	06
5	Acute bronchitis	04	02
6	Pneumonia	10	05
7	Viral pyrexia	09	05
8	Dengue fever	08	04
9	UTI	19	09
10	Meningitis	03	01
11	Sinusitis	07	03

The co morbid conditions prevailing in both overall populations & study were having diabetes mellitus, hypertension. The details of other Co- morbid conditions were given The high incidence of diabetes as a co morbidity contributed to the higher chance of infections and hence increased antibiotic use.

Table.6.CO-Morbid Condition.

S.No.	Co morbid conditions	n = 49
1	Diabetes	31
2	Hypertension	11
3	BPH	02
4	CHF	02
5	Liver cirrhosis	01
6	Hepatomegaly	01
7	Peptic ulcer	01

Totally 553 different drugs were prescribed to the overall population. the details of other drugs prescribed were given in the Table.7.

Table. 7. Drugs Prescribed.

S. No.	Drugs	Overall n = 553	Study n =270
1	Anti ulcer	90 (16.27)	44 (16.29)
2	Multivitamins	92 (16.63)	45 (16.68)
3	Analgesics	84 (15.19)	41 (15.18)
4	Anti asthmatics	63 (11.39)	31 (11.48)
5	Anti diabetics	55 (9.95)	27 (10.0)
6	NSAIDS	28 (5.06)	14 (5.18)
7	Laxatives	34 (6.15)	17 (6.29)
8	Anti tubercular	30 (5.42)	13 (4.81)
10	Antihypertensive	22 (3.98)	11 (4.07)
11	Diuretics	14 (2.53)	07 (2.6)
12	Anti emetics	11 (1.99)	05 (1.85)
15	Antihistamine	06 (1.08)	03 (1.11)
20	Antiamoebics	12 (2.16)	06 (2.22)
21	Antispasmodics	04 (0.7)	02 (0.74)
22	Alkalisers	08 (1.44)	04 (1.48)

Totally 225 antibiotics were prescribed for the overall population and the mean was 2.28 ± 1.08 with the maximum of 4 antibiotics and the minimum of 1 antibiotic. In study population, 110 antibiotics were prescribed. The mean was 2.32 ± 0.56 with the maximum of 2 antibiotics and the minimum 1 antibiotic. The same was shown in the table No.8.

Table.8. Antibiotics prescribed.

S. No.	Number of antibiotics Prescribed	Overall (n=225)	Study (n=110)
1	1	05	02
2	2	28	14
3	3	08	04
4	6	01	-

Route of administration

Totally 225 antibiotics were prescribed for the overall population, 61.65% were administrated intravenously and 39.35% of oral antibiotics. The study population had, 73.63% of intravenously administrated and 26.27% orally. A study by Briquet et al (2008) evaluated the impact of converting IV administration of antibiotics over oral administration. The reported advantages were less preparation time, easier administration, lower risk of complications and lesser cost.

Organisms Isolated:

In the study population (n=49). Six different organisms were isolated. The major organisms identified were E.coli, staphylococcus aureus, staphylococcus pneumonia, klebsiella pneumonia, pseudomonas, and Streptococcus species. This same was shown in the figure No.2.

Figure No. 2. Major organism isolated (n=128).

Specimens:

The organisms isolated were obtained from different specimen. The following Figure No.: 6, reveals the different specimens from which they were isolated.

Table.9. Organisms Isolated.

S.No	Specimen	n = 49	Overall
01	Blood	06	12
02	Pus	08	16
03	Urine	21	43
04	Sputum	14	29

Specimens Vs Organism:

E.coli was highly prevalent in urine sample; Staphylococcus pneumonia was most common in sputum. klebsiella pneumonia was highly seen in pus cells and staphylococcus aureus was present more in blood, pus, and sputum respectively.

Emergence of Resistance:

In the study, culture study reports reveal the emergence of resistance of micro organisms. E.coli was resistance to netillin, klebsiella pneumonia to meropenum, staphylococcus pneumonia to Augmentin, Staphylococcus Aureus to ciprofloxacin, pseudomonas to cefoperazone, and streptococcus species to nalixidic acid.

Appropriateness of antibiotics use in different departments:

From the overall population, 44 were hospitalized in General Medicine department, 27 in Care & Supportive centre and 29 in surgical departments. Rational use of antibiotics was high in (83.47%) General Medicine, 77.77 % in Care & Supportive centre and 82.66% in surgical department in Table.10.

Table.10.Appropriateness of antibiotics use in different departments:

S. No.	Departments	Rational %	Irrational %
1	General medicine (44)	83.47	16.53
2	Care & Supportive centre (27)	77.77	22.23
3	Surgical (29)	82.66	17.34

Categories of antibiotics prescribed:

The most commonly used antibiotics were Cephalosporin's (27.83%), Aminoglycosides (24.14%), Quionolones (15.64%), Carbapenems (7.62%), Penicillin (5.78%), and Macrolides (4.72%). The same was also reported with Ayse erbay et al (2003) in which most commonly prescribed antibiotics was Cephalosporin's. Most appropriately used antibiotics were Carbapenems (100%), Penicillin (78.78%), Aminoglycosides (52.27%), Cephalosporin's (50.32%), Macrolides (43.33%) and Quionolones (40.86%). The same was given in Table No. 11. A similar result as that of table No.11. were reported by Ayse erbay et al (2003) in which most commonly prescribed antibiotics was Cephalosporin's.

Table. 10. Appropriateness of Antibiotics used in different departments.

S. No.	Categories	Antibiotics	Overall (n=225)	Study(n=110)
1	Amino-glycosides	Amikacin	54 (24.0)	26 (23.64)
2	Cephalosporins	Ceftriaxone	29 (12.9)	15 (13.62)
3		Cifipime	20 (8.9)	11 (10.0)
4		Cefixime	05 (2.22)	02 (1.8)
5		Cefatoxime	03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)
6		Cefoperazone	02	01
7		Cefaclor	-	-
8		Fluoroquinolones	Levofloxacin	26 (11.56)
9	Ciprofloxacin		04 (2.01)	02 (1.8)
10	Prulifloxacin		03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)
11	Norfloxacin		-	-
12	Ofloxacin		-	-
13	Penicillin	Amoxicillin	13 (5.78)	08 (7.32)
13	Carbapenems	Imipenem	17 (7.6)	10 (8.48)
14		Piperacillin	21 (9.34)	10 (9.09)
15	Macrolides	Azithromycin	09 (3.98)	04 (3.62)
16		Clarithromycin	03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)
17	Anti tuberculosis	Isoniazid	04 (2.01)	02 (1.8)
18		Pyrazinamide	03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)
19		Rifampicin	03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)
20		Ethambutol	03 (1.8)	01 (0.91)

Therapeutic indications:

Indications for antibiotic use were grouped into three categories: empirical (based on clinical evidence of infection), Prophylactic (administration of antibiotics without evidence of infection) and specific use (based on culture report). Of the prescribed antibiotics, 37% were administered empirically, 15% for Prophylactic purpose and 48% according to the culture results. Rational use of antibiotics was significantly higher when culture reports were considered than when given empirically or used prophylactic ally.

DISCUSSION

Based on our study findings majority of patients who was admitted in the hospital & were receiving antibiotics were within the age group of 51-65 years and belonging to males and mostly smokers who were prone to LRTI &UTI and mostly infected organism was found to be E.Coli and widely used antibiotic was found to be amikacin followed by cephalosporins. Our study is in concordance with the study done by J. Mohan et al (2011) entitled as "observational drug utilization study on complicated UTI" which concluded that most of study subject wear in the age group of 18-64 years ,either gender that UTI, majority of organisms were sensitive to amikacin and third generation cephalosporins like cefotaxime, ceftriaxone and cefoperazone, this study also showed that the most common agent causing UTI was E.coli with the most frequently used antibiotic being amikacin.In our study we also found that majority of patients were receiving atleast two antibiotics and less were prescribed with one antibiotic. This finding was in concordance with the study done by Preetha et al (2011) on "prospective observational study about prescribing pattern of antibiotics used in the management of infectious disease" which showed majority was on combination therapy.

CONCLUSION

The rational use of antibiotics will be increasingly supported by the diagnosis of bacterial infections, based on the culture sensitivity report to identify optimum treatment. Antibiotics were prescribed on clinical judgement in majority of patients rather than obtaining the culture sensitivity reports. Educational interventions emphasizing rational prescribing, along a multidirectional effort to create an update local formulary and a strict antibiotic prescribing policy can help significantly to overcome these problems and to reduce the extent of resistance to antibiotics and most effective in preventing the resistance of microorganisms is to ensure appropriate antibiotic use. In order to prevent use of antibiotics for inappropriate indications and to prevent economic loss, the sale of antibiotics without prescriptions should be restricted and prescriptions should always include the period, the dosage and also the number of drugs required. Recommended future research.

Abbreviations-

UTI	: Urinary Tract Infection
SPSS	: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
ADR	: Adverse Drug Reactions
ANOVA	: Analysis of variance

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Conflicts of interest: None

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